

AN ETHICAL CODES OF CONDUCT OF LIFE (*SADVRITTA*) IN LIGHTS OF
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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is the science of life with the primary aim of maintain the health and prevention of diseases. To maintain long live healthy life should follow code of conducts (*Sadvritta*) in this fast and furious, work loaded, stressful era. *Sadvritta* is mainly concern of behavioral regulation and mental discipline regarding what to do or what not to do. In this review study dealing about codes of conducts of life, its principals, and rules regarding various types of conducts like hygiene, speech, diet, urges, general rule, relationship, social relation and behavior, *Achara Rasayana*, *Vega dharana*, etc.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, Code of Conduct, Healthy life, *Swasthavritta*, *Sadvritta*.**INTRODUCTION**

In Ayurveda, *Swasthavritta* is branch of sciences which deals with healthy living practices by focusing on maintenance of healthy life styles to combat diseases and overall wellbeing. *Swasthavritta* gives importance to diet, exercise and healthy lifestyle to maintain good health. According to *Sharngdhar Samhita* 'No one is immortal in universe.' It's impossible to prevent death, but it is possible to prevent disease so one should try for that which is preventable.^[1] In era of modernization, one should follow *Sadvritta* to maintainance of our health. Take care of our body by avoiding all other things because if the body is not healthy then nothing is existed.^[2] *Sadvritta* not only includes mental faculties, but also rules related with hygiene, religion, food, sexual activity, and exercise, etc. which can prevent physical, psychological & Psychosomatic diseases.^[3]

Nirukti of Sadvritta^[4]

Sadvritta comprises of 2 words 'Sat' meaning good & 'vritta' meaning *achara* or regimen. Association with good people leads to development of good behavior, which can be considered as *Sadvritta*.

For maintaining health of *Indriya* (Sense organ) & *Mana* (Mind) one has to observe following rules.

- ✓ Proper interaction of sense organ. (*Samyaka yoga of Indriya*)
- ✓ Performing of different actions after proper thoughtful analysis by his intelligence.
- ✓ Acting against qualities of place, season and one's constitution. (*Desha-Kala-Aatma-Guna-Viparitaupasana*)

Principles of *Sadvritta*^[5]

Aacharya Charaka, mentioned some principles about *Sadvritta*; They are.

- ✓ Word of Nobel persons is considered as best adoptable behavior.
- ✓ Happiness is best among nourishing things.
- ✓ Detachment is best among enhancers of nourishment.
- ✓ Boycott who does not believe in God.
- ✓ Greed is one among prime trouble maker.
- ✓ Wicked word which leads to harmful effects.
- ✓ Avoiding *Pradynaparadha* (Intellectual errors)

By proper following principles of *Sadvritta* which leads to prevents many diseases.

Discussion on *Sadvritta*: (Codes of Conduct of Life)

As per Ayurvedic classical texts various types of *Sadvritta* (code of conducts of life) explained in details but which is possible to follow in the present era of life is given below.

❖ Practice to prevent psychological disturbances^[6]

- ✓ Worship of God, cow, brahmin, teachers, elders, sages, fire and wear auspicious herbs.
- ✓ One should do Vedic rituals in morning & evening twice.
- ✓ Perform religious ceremony, donations, respect the guests, offer *Pinda dāna* to fore fathers, have a faith on God, obedient, elders and sages.
- ✓ Pacify the anger of angry person, care for suffering person, always speak truth, avoids the words and factors leading to anger, greed etc.

❖ Rule of Hygiene^[6]

- ✓ Clean excretory orifices, hands, feet's frequently, Cut hairs and nails thrice in 15 days.
- ✓ Wear clean cloths, apply scent, comb hairs, apply oil to head, ear, nose & feet every day.
- ✓ Avoid place with dirty cloths, bones, impure hairs, garbage, ash, place of bath & worship.
- ✓ Not release flatus with sound, not yawn, sneeze without covering mouth, not have relation with bad conduct persons.

❖ Rule of Diet^[6]

- ✓ Not take food without bath, chanting of mantra, praying God and proper handwash.
- ✓ Not consume food completely except curds, honey, salt, *saktu* and ghee.
- ✓ Avoid stale food purchasing except meat, ginger, dry vegetables, fruits, & sweets.
- ✓ Not eat *saktu* without mixing with Ghee, sugar or in night, after taking full meal.

❖ Rule of Urges^[6]

- ✓ Not sneeze, eat or sleep in prone pose, Not do any work with holding natural urges.
- ✓ Not spit, micturate, defecate Infront of wind, fire, water, sun, on roadsides & public place.

❖ Rule of Speech^[6]

- ✓ Speech less, timely, conducive, and in sweet way. Not speak lies, point out mistake of others, not disclose of secretes.

❖ Rules regarding relation with females^[6]

- ✓ Not insult female or depend on them or reveals secretes to them.
- ✓ Not indulge physically with menstruating female, diseased, impure, not good looking, bad conducts females. Avoid sex while impure, without desire, erection and under pressure of urge for urine.

❖ Rules regarding social relationship^[7]

- ✓ Should follow path of *Bramhcharya*, Knowledge, Friendship, Donation, Happiness, Detachment & peace.

❖ Rule regarding study^[8]

- ✓ Avoid study in unnatural climatic conditions.
- ✓ Not chant incomplete *mantras* or without proper voice.

❖ Rule regarding behavior^[6]

- ✓ Not desire for other money, wife or wealth. Not interact with bad, mad, mean-minded peoples and not indulge in sinful acts.
- ✓ Not go to temple, scared tree, cremations and slaughter houses in night.

❖ Rule regarding fire worship^[7]

- ✓ Not offer ghee, rice, grains, Tila, grass and mustard when it's in impure condition, etc.

❖ General rules^[8]

- ✓ Not waste time, break the rules in classics, should not take food, read or indulge sexual activity in evening time.
- ✓ Not have ego, jealousy, or abuse brahmins, & beat cow with stick, should not move away from relatives, loved once who help in difficulty & knows the secretes.
- ✓ Always have faith in cause & effect, one should lose spirit or remember the insults done earlier.

❖ *Achara Rasayana*^[9]

- ✓ Always speak truth, avoid anger, alcohol, sexual act & violence. Should be peaceful, avoid exertion, speak sweet, practice *Japa* and cleanness. Be courageous, generous, respect god, elders, be aways from cruelty and always kind to all.
- ✓ Sleep and get up on proper time, take a milk and ghee daily. Have a knowledge about time, place, proper planning with intelligence.

❖ *Dharaniya Vega*^[7, 10]

- ✓ Control urges of greed, grief, fear, anger, ego excessive attachment and desire things possessed by others. Avoid harsh words, back biting, lying and use of untimely words.
- ✓ Violences against others, desire for other women and stealing should be controlled.

Role of *Sadvritta* for prevention of diseases^[11]

- ✓ It leads to prevention of Psychological and physical as well as psychosomatic disorders.
- ✓ *Sadvritta* with *Aacharya Rasayana & Dharaniya Vega* with avoiding *Pradynaparadha* which prevents multifactorial diseases, where involvement of mind is invariably present at one or the other stage of disease.
- ✓ One who has good memory power with knowledge of regimen, good conduct can remember rules well and prevent diseases.
- ✓ *Sadvritta* (Good conduct) prevents lifestyle diseases likes as stress induced diseases, sleep disorders, behavioral diseases, etc.

CONCLUSION

A person practicing *Sadvritta*, regimen which are wholesome for sense organs, good memory power, knowledge about place, time and himself as well as observance of codes of conducts should able to avoid and prevent diseases.

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